

JOB STRESS AMONG SCHOOL TEACHERS OF JAMMU REGION OF JAMMU AND KASHMIR

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Abstract:

Stress is an organism's total response to environmental demands or pressures. When stress was first studied in 1950's, the term was used to denote both the causes and the experienced effects of these pressures. Stress may be good or bad. More recently, however, the word stressor has been used for the stimulus that provokes a stress response. The aim of the study was to find out the factor that creates stress among school teachers in Jammu region. The 60 respondents were selected by random sampling method. Data was analysed with the help of factor analysis and Chi square test. The most important factor that creates stress is salary and other benefits, work load, and job security. So by improving these factors job stress can be reduced among the school teachers. The results of this study may be helpful for school administrations and higher authorities to make best possible policies for teachers.

Key Words: Job Stress, School Teachers, Gender, Jammu, J&K

1. Introduction:

Stress in 21st century is not something new, not anything unknown. Stress has been experienced since time immortal but its toll is higher than ever before. Among the hardest parts of living in the modern world is stress. With the worries about the work, the environment, the economy, natural disasters, terrorism and general state of the world, it seems that there is no end to the number of things to worry about. Though we cannot control many of these things, they still weigh on our minds and cause us stress. However, despite these concerns, we should try to avoid stress. The modern world which is said to be a work of achievements is also a world of stress. One finds stress everywhere, whether it is within family, business organisation/enterprise or any other or economic activity. Indian society is undergoing rapid social changes and these changes have brought in their wake a number of stresses for the community a large. Thus it is not surprising that stress has been rising with the advancement of present century which has been called the "Age of anxiety and stress". The stress induced due to the roles performed by the individuals as employees has been a potent organisational stressor (Khan et.al, 1964; Srivastava, 2007). The outcomes of which have been found to be costly to the organisation (Fisher and Gitelson, 1983). A person performs various roles that are centred on the self and are at varying distances from self. The relationships, the role space, which then is dynamic interrelationship between the self and the various roles an individual occupies. The focus of roles can be useful in planning organisational effectiveness. Herzberg (1968) drew attention to the need for humanising the need for involving jobs and giving more dignity to them. The work redesigning movement highlighted the need for involving job holders in work - related decisions and giving them more autonomy in work- related matters. A New Delhi NGO Vikas School of Development reported that in 1996 a total of 4,100 persons contacted its helpline for people on the verge of committing suicide (Agrawal, 2001). This figure definitely requires some serious thinking. Stress in India can take many forms – for example, stress among the youth, adults, unemployed stress, job stress, marital stress, health stress etc. It is becoming increasingly clear that youth of India face tremendous pressure regarding career, parental expectations and personal identity crisis so much. So that in recent years, numerous voluntary organisations have come forward to help youth cope with stresses in life.

Stress is a subject which is hard to avoid. The term is discussed not only in our everyday conversation but has become enough of a public issue to attract widespread media attention, whether it is radio, T.V, newspapers, or magazines, issues of stress figures, everywhere. Different people have different views about it as stress can be experienced from a variety of sources. With increasing concern about quality of life, concern in stress has also increased. One has to give attention to role stress and extreme negative effect of stress- the burnout phenomenon. Various researches have shown that burnout is experienced most in professions dealing with human services and teaching being one of that, is facing these problems (Joshi, 1999). According to Hans Selye, a pioneer researcher in stress reaction, "stress is the human response to changes that occur as a part of daily living". "Stress comes from any situation or a circumstance that requires behavioural adjustment. Any change, either good or bad, is stressful, and whether it's a positive or negative change, the physiological response is the same" (Lazarus, 2000)

Review of Related Literature:

Literature review which covers ways for an understanding of the area of the research which is already undertaken on the potential areas which are yet to be covered. In this way an attempt has made to a brief survey of the work undertaken on the field of stress management and employee performance.

Ansari (1991) had studied the nature and extent of stress in agricultural university teachers. The result revealed that the correlation between the nature of stress and qualification of teachers in different cadres was found to be non - significant.

Ammabhavi and Triveni (2000) in their study found that age, sex, coping strategies of the employees have not influence their occupational stress and role stress. Younger people experience more stress as compared to the older people.

Gaur and Dhawan (2000) examined that the relationship between works related stressors and adaptation pattern among women started professionals. It showed that the four professionals groups have started almost similar level of stress except in the categories of career development and stressors specific to working people.

Bindu and Sudeesh Kumar (2006) focused on the relationship between job satisfaction and stress coping skills among 500 primary school teachers in India. The study found a positive relationship between job satisfaction and stress coping skills and teachers who create a supportive organisational climate, enrich the design of tasks, reduce conflicts, and are provided guidance tend to more satisfied and better equipped cope with stress.

Kour and Kour (2007) attempted to make a study on the occupational stress and burnout among women police. The results concluded that police occupation is more stressful occupation and as the occupational stress increases, the level of burnout increases.

Azar Eskandaricharati (2014) had investigated the organisational characteristics and their relationship with organisational commitment of the teachers of three Universities of Hyderabad. The results revealed that those who have higher job satisfaction, participation in decision making and higher sense of belongingness are more committed to the organisation.

Research Mythology:

- ✓ **Sample UNIT and Sample Size:** The sample selected for this study was 60 school teachers from Jammu region of J&K. A sample of 60 respondents was chosen through the random sampling technique.
- ✓ **Research Instruments and Data Analysis Tools:** The study was conducted with pre structured questionnaire. To facilitate answering, the questions were developed in simple words. The information collected from the survey has been analysed using different techniques. The various statistical tools as factor analysis and Chi-square test have been used in the present study.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the factors those cause job stress.
- ✓ To suggest some measures to reduce the level of job stress in schools.

Hypothesis Formulation:

- ✓ There is no significant of factors (Salary and other benefits, working conditions, relations with colleagues, job security and workload) on the job stress of school teachers.

Data Analysis and Interpretation: A total of 60 teacher respondent participated in the survey. Most of the respondents participated in the study were male employees (60%) and most of the respondents were working for more than 10 years. By doing factor analysis and chi-square test it has seen that most important factors as perceived by the school teachers as discussed as under:

Salary and Other Benefits: The factor salary and other benefits is the most important factor. It includes training and experience, income alone is enough to meet the family needs , performance appraisal and promotions are based upon objective criteria.

Working Conditions: The factor working condition offered the organisation and it includes work timings, insufficient time for lesson preparation, unable to get sufficient breaks, personal harassment, lack of colourful reading materials, poor infrastructure.

Relations with Colleagues: The factor explains anger and friction between the colleagues and least interference of colleagues in case of difficulty.

Job Security: This factor explains namely no worry about termination of job, income from job is sufficient to meet family needs and institute offer training and development programmes.

Workload: This factor suggests lack of time for lesson preparation, excess official workload due to non availability of clerical staff, inclusion of daily and weekly diaries of lesson plan extra duties during elections .

Discussion and Findings:

Four factors have been found that creates job stress among the school teachers i.e working conditions, relations with colleagues, job security and workload. Salary and other benefits plays important role in one's economic status if not satisfied it creates stress.

Conclusion:

It is concluded from the study that salary and other benefits, working conditions, relations with colleagues, job security and work load are the most important factors that create stress among the school teachers. A model can be formed with the help of factors found in the study.

Recommendations

- ✓ Educational institutions and organisations must improve the salary structure according to the cost of living.
- ✓ Salary allowance and pension benefits must be provided so that teacher feels secured.
- ✓ Employee should be provided professional advancement opportunities.
- ✓ Promotion criteria should be based on certain departmental exams not on seniority.

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